

Supplementary Figure 1

Variant allele frequencies of *EPAS1* variants in germline samples from 7 CCHD cases

* Variant allele frequency (VAF) in seven germline samples is plotted for all 12 *EPAS1* variants detected in CCHD-PPGLs. Red point represents the VAF of identical variants which was observed in the tumor from the corresponding case. VAFs of artifact variants in all germline samples were also shown on the right side of the figure.